

Determination of the Physicochemical Properties of Soil Amended with Cassava Mill Effluent in Mosogar Area of Delta State

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Abstract

This research studied the effect of cassava mill effluent on the physicochemical properties of soil samples from specific locations in Mosogar community, of Ethiope West Local Government Area, Delta State, Nigeria. Sample collection and analyses were done, using standard methods of analysis for physicochemical properties: pH, Organic Matter (OM), Organic Carbon (OC), Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC), etc and heavy metals: Iron (Fe), Copper (Cu), Zinc (Zn), Manganese (Mn) and Lead (Pb) content. The physicochemical properties of the effluent were also characterized and soil samples were treated with the cassava mill effluent at different rates of 10, 20, 30 and 40% after 3 and 6 months respectively. Triplicate analysis of the treated samples revealed pH result of 6.2 ± 0.1 - 6.4 ± 0.2 at 30% after 6 months of treatment %OC, 6.4 ± 0.5 - 14.1 ± 0.2 with 40% treatment after 3 months. CEC, 30.8 - 62.4 (meq/100g) with 40% treatment after 6 months. Heavy metals result showed Fe reduction, 145 ± 0.2 - 113.2 ± 0.1 mg/kg at 10% after 6 months. Cu, 112 ± 0.2 - 8.5 ± 0.2 mg/kg at 40% after 3 months. and Pb, 14.7 ± 0.1 - 1.0 ± 0.1 mg/kg at 10% after 3 months. Zn increase, 8.2 ± 0.5 - 20.6 ± 0.4 mg/kg at 40% after 6 months. Mn increase, 12.1 ± 0.1 - 24.3 ± 0.5 mg/kg at 40% after 3 months This indicates a good soil amendment capacity of cassava mill effluent over a period of time. However, it should be cautiously applied because of its inconsistent interactions with soil heavy metals.

Keywords: Physicochemical Properties, Soil Samples, Cassava Mill Effluent, Soil Amendment

Introduction

Soil deterioration is a decline in soil quality or fertility, which could be immediate or gradual. This process can be physical, biological, or chemical and is usually caused by poor soil management which could be as a result of over-cultivation, improper disposal of waste, industrialization or even population growth. Inappropriate management of agricultural land has caused a reduction in soil quality in many areas of the world and Ihejirika, Onwudike, Nwaogu, Emereibeole, Ebe and Ejiogu, (2012) opine that human use of land and other resources has released hazardous materials into the environment. Civilization, misuse and exploitation have polluted our soils; atmospheric pollution has already had global effects on the composition of soils, that it is increasingly difficult to encounter uncontaminated soils (Balba, 1995).

The major consequences of soil decline are poor soil fertility, erosion and general soil destabilization and this has forced the land use stakeholders to consider ways of improving soil quality through organic fertilizers (Channarayappa & Biradar, 2018). Organic fertilizers are described as organic substances added to the soil to increase the quality of the soil and also improve the yield of crops. Organic wastes are known to be very

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vital sources of nutrients and minerals for plants generally and Fakorede, Igbenegbhu and Odeyemi (2014), agrees they are good soil conditioners. These include, fish pond effluents, poultry manure, palm, cassava mill effluents, rubber mill effluent, oil mill effluents abattoir waste and crop residues. Large quantities of these wastes, are produced and discharged into farms and they become environmental pollutants. However, Bhunia, Bhowmik & Mukherjee, (2022), believe that the deliberate addition of these wastes is found to increase soil physicochemical properties, especially those known to be fertility indicators like nitrogen, phosphorus, organic carbon, exchangeable bases and other trace elements. According to Akpan, Solomon & Bello (2011), cassava is regarded as a typical subsistence crop in the tropics and have about 40 varieties with some varieties being developed through genetic enhancement. Cassava is an important staple food and in the tropical world, it ranks fourth in importance after rice, wheat and maize (Rosemary, Onuorah & Abba, 2024), and plays a critical role (Reusmanta, Ahmad, Raya & Ibrahim, 2019) in global food security due to its adaptability to various climates and high calorie content.

Recent studies indicate about 45% of the cassava tubers are sold to get income by the farmers in Nigeria and cassava production has witnessed an increase over the past thirty years. In Ekpoma area of Edo State, the total production from 1995 to 2002 was over one million metric tons (Ebhoaye & Dada, 2003). Due to its widespread consumption, and its major post-harvest processing which involves the use of traditional grating or modern milling machines; effluents are obtained from the production and are channeled most times inappropriately into the soil. Nweke and Onuoha (2024), opined that cassava mill effluent obtained from traditional grating or discharged during processing, is a major cause of environmental degradation as they contaminate farmlands, air, streams and negatively impact our general ecosystem especially soils around the location of processing or along discharge routes.

The cassava effluent has great influence on the chemical properties of the soil. Studies by Ebhoaye and Dada (2004) using fresh cassava processing effluent and effluent obtained from a cassava processing mill in Ekpoma, Edo State showed increase in the level of pH, organic matter, and heavy metal in the soil samples. Akpan *et al* (2011) believe only ph, organic carbon and nitrogen increased significantly while CEC, available phosphorus, magnesium and potassium reduced in soils with cassava mill effluent. Nweke and Onuoha (2024) agrees the cassava mill effluent introduced to selected communities in Abakiliki area of Ebonyi State, actually increased the physicochemical properties, but they insist the increase in physicochemical properties are not sustainable after 3 months. While increase in soil physicochemical properties are good fertility indicators, a significant increase in the heavy metals content (which may be present in cassava mill effluent) can be very detrimental to soil health. Generally, poor waste management strategies frequently have negative environmental impacts, therefore, effluents from cassava mill and other organic effluents should be attended to properly, otherwise, it will be detrimental to the biotic system (Frey *et al.*, 2020).

This study therefore seeks to use cassava mill effluent which is (an established soil pollutant) as an amendment to improve soil physicochemical properties and technically increase the fertility of the amended soil. It also intends to study the ability of the effluent in reducing soil heavy metals content, hence the selection of specific sampling locations.

Materials and Methods

Materials

The soil samples were collected from farms behind Government Secondary School, Mosogar (at coordinates: 5.8539N, 5.7051E) and Department of works Delta State College of Education, Mosogar (at coordinates: 5.8572N, 5.7064E). Mosogar is in Ethiope-West Local Government Area of Delta State and is bounded to the west by Oghara town, to the east by Jesse town, to the north by Edo state and to the south by ethiope river. The topography is stable and soil is well drained, which makes it appropriate for agricultural purposes. Sample site was selected due to their proximities to areas where there might be a high soil pollution due to certain activities including metals works.

The sampling was done using the soil auger to a depth of 10-15cm and kept in 25kg capacity container. The untreated soil samples were crushed with the laboratory mortar and pestle, sieved using a 2 mm sieve, labelled and kept in polythene bags in preparation for analysis. Grab sampling method was used for the collection of Cassava mill effluent from three cassava processing plants in Mosogar and stored in 25kg container for one month to enable adequate fermentation

Methods

The soil samples were analyzed in two stages: pre-treatment and post-treatment analysis

Pre-treatment analysis

The soil samples were analyzed for physicochemical properties: Ph, %OC, CEC and heavy metals content

Determination of soil pH

20ml of distilled water was added to 20 g of the sieved soil sample, stirred continuously for about 5minutes in a 250ml beaker, allowed to stand for 30 minutes with occasional stirring with glass rod. The pH meter electrodes were then inserted into the soil suspension and pH value displayed on the meter was recorded.

Determination of Organic Carbon

The crushed soil sample was grounded further using porcelain mortar and pestle to pass through 0.5mm sieve and analysis carried out with the dichromate oxidation method described in the Laboratory Testing Procedure for Soil and Water Sample Analysis (2009), and used by Ikiriko, Kamalu and Joseph (2022).

Determination of Nitrogen

Regular Macro-Kjedahl Method as reproduced by Asagba *et al.*, (2007), was used for this analysis. 0.2g of the crushed and sieved soil sample was introduced into a 100ml digestion tube containing a mixture of selenium catalyst (one tablet) and 4ml conc. H₂SO₄. The tubes were heated on the digestion block until the solution became clear after which 10ml of distilled water was added. The solution filtered into a 100ml volumetric flask and another 10ml of distilled water added with 4.5ml of alkaline phenate, 3ml of potassium sodium tartrate, 2.5 of sodium hypochlorite with continuous stirring until colour develops. The graph of absorbance versus concentration was plotted and slope reciprocal was calculated.

Calculation

$$N\% = \frac{A \times S_R \times V_1 \times V_2}{W_S \times V_3 \times 106} \times 100$$

Where

A = Absorbance

S_R = Slope Reciprocal

V_1 = Volume of extract

V_2 = Volume of colour developed

W_S = Weight of sample

Determination of Available Phosphorus

Using Laboratory Testing Procedure for Soil and Water Sample Analysis (2009) as described by Asagba *et al.*, (2007), and Ikiriko *et al.*, (2022), 5g of processed soil was weighed into a 150ml plastic bottle and shaken for 5 minutes while adding 35ml of 0.03M NH₄F for 1 minute and filtered Whatman filter paper was used to filter the content and 5ml of the filtrate was pipetted into a 100ml polyethylene bottle. 4ml of phosphorus colour developer was added a this was allowed to stay for 1 minute and then read at 882 nm using Unico, UV/Visible spectrophotometer.

The absorbance of standard and samples were read.

Calculation

$$Pmg/kg - \frac{A \times SR \times V_1 \times V_2}{W_s \times V_3}$$

Where

A = Absorbance

S_R = Slope Reciprocal

V_1 = Volume of extract

V_3 = Aliquot used

V_2 = Volume of colour developed

W_s = Weight of sample

Determination of Exchangeable Cation (Na, K, Ca, Mg)

According to Laboratory Testing Procedure for Soil and Water Sample Analysis (2009) and described by Akpan *et al.*, (2011), the crushed soil sample was grounded further using porcelain mortar and pestle to pass through 0.5mm sieve. According to 5g of the soil sample was weighed into 250ml flasks with lids. 100ml of NH₄ OAC solution (pH7) was added into the bottles, with shaking and the content shaken for 30 minutes. The content was filtered through Whatman No. 42 filter paper. The soil extract was used for the determination of Na, K, Ca, and Mg. 100ml of Ammonium acetate (NH₄ OAC) solution without the soil puts in plastic tubes represented the black samples.

The standard working solution were measured to calibrate the instruments (Flame photometer for Na, and K, atomic absorption spectrophotometer for Ca and Mg) to fall within the measurable range of the flame photometer and atomic.

Absorption spectrophotometer, the soil extracts were diluted as required and 5ml of the soil extract solution was introduced into 50ml volumetric flask. 1ml of 2.8% lanthanum chloride solution was added and the content diluted with IM NH₄OAc extraction solution. The solution was then aspirated into the instrument for the different determinations. Graph of absorbance versus concentration was plotted from which the slope reciprocal was calculated.

Calculation

The concentration of K, Na, Ca and Mg in the soil samples expressed in milli-equivalent (meq) per 100g soil is calculated as follows:

$$\frac{A \times SR \times V_1}{W_s}$$

Where A, S_R, V₁, W_S, are as previously defined

$$\frac{\text{The cation exchange capacity expressed in milli-equivalent per 100g (meq/100g) soil} = \text{Cation(meq)}/100g}{E}$$

Where, E = Equivalent weight of Cation x 10

Determination of Moisture Content

An empty crucible was dried in a thermostatically controlled oven at 110°C and allowed to stay for 5 minutes, and the weight was recorded (W_1). 10g of soil sample was weighed into the dry empty crucible, covered and the new weight was taken as W_2 . The crucible and soil sample was put in the oven at the same 110° and allowed to stay for 24 hours until a steady-state weight was attained. The new weight was recorded as W_3 Average of three determinations was taken as the moisture content.

Calculation

The moisture content

$$W = \frac{W_2 - W_3}{W_3 - W_1} \times 100$$

Determination of Total Heavy Metals

1.0g of air-dried soil was weighed and transferred to a 250ml conical flask. Measured volumes of well-mixed acids; perchloric acids ($HClO_4$) nitric HNO_3 in the ratio of 1:2 were weighed into the flask containing the soil sample in the fume hood. The sample was heated at a constant temperature for about (15-20min) in the hot plate until a white fume was observed.

On cooling, 20ml of distilled water was added and boiled to bring the metal into solution. After further cooling, the solution was filtered through Whatman 42 filter paper in a 100ml volumetric flask and was made to mark with distilled water and then transferred to 100ml plastic can for AAS analysis. The heavy metals analyzed include Fe, Zn, Mn, Pb, Cu.

Post-treatment analysis: The raw soil samples were then treated with various percentages of the effluent at the rates of 10%, 20%, 30%, 40% and left to cure for a period of 3-6 months. At 3 and 6 months respectively, the treated soil samples were again subjected to the same physicochemical and heavy metals analysis as the raw samples and result obtained are shown in **Table 3**.

Results

Table 1: Physio-chemical Properties of Untreated Mosogar Soil Sample

SOIL PROPERTIES	RESULTS
Ph	6.2±0.1
Fe (mg/kg)	145±0.2
Cu (mg/kg)	112±0.2
Zn (mg/kg)	8.2±0.5
Mn (mg/kg)	12.1±0.1
Pb (mg/kg)	14.7±0.1
%OM	11.02±0.2
%OC	6.4±0.5
%N	2.1±0.1
P(meq/100g)	1.5±0.1
Mg(meq/100g)	4.1±0.1
Ca(meq/100g)	6.9±0.4
K(meq/100g)	10.1±0.1

Na(meq/100g)	9.9±0.0
CEC (meq/100g)	30.835

Table 2: Result of Physicochemical Properties of Cassava Mill Effluent

PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES	RESULT
Ph	4.6±0.1
Fe (mg/kg)	20.12±
Zn (mg/kg)	6.5±0.2
Mn (mg/kg)	8.8±0.1
Pb (mg/kg)	3.0±0.1
%MC	86.1±0.5
%OC	16.5±0.2
%N	0.01±0.0
P(meq/100g)	0.1±0.0
Mg(meq/100g)	0.1±0.0
Ca(meq/100g)	1.±0.1
K(meq/100g)	0.8±0.3
Na(meq/100g)	0.75±0.0

Table 3: Result of Physicochemical Properties of Soil amended with Cassava Mill Effluent

SOIL PPTY	CONTROL	3 MONTHS POST-TREATMENT OF CASSAVA MILL EFFLUENT				6 MONTHS POST-TREATMENT OF CASSAVA MILL EFFLUENT			
		10%	20%	30%	40%	10%	20%	30%	40%
Ph	6.2±0.1	6.1±0.3	5.9±0.4	5.7±0.4	5.2±0.1	6.2±0.3	5.8±0.3	6.4±0.2	5.9±0.3
Fe (mg/kg)	145±0.2	113.2±0.1	115.1±0.1	118.4±0.3	124.2±0.1	114±0.2	115.6±0.2	117.8±0.4	124.5±0.3
Cu (mg/kg)	112±0.2	8.5±0.2	8.8±0.3	9.1±0.3	10.4±0.1	8.6±0.5	9.0±0.1	9.5±0.2	10.1±0.5
Zn (mg/kg)	8.2±0.5	13.2±0.3	15.0±0.4	17.4±0.1	20.5±0.1	13.3±0.1	15.2±0.5	17.3±0.6	20.6±0.9
Mn (mg/kg)	12.1±0.1	16.2±0.2	18.2±0.4	21.3±0.1	24.3±0.5	16.1±0.3	17.3±0.5	21.0±0.3	23.7±0.3
Pb (mg/kg)	14.7±0.1	1.0±0.5	1.6±0.5	2.1±0.1	2.6±0.5	1.1±0.3	1.4±0.3	2.0±0.3	2.5±0.5
%Mc	20.1±0.4	20.5±0.2	21.5±0.1	22.6±0.2	25.9±0.1	20.4±0.2	21.4±0.1	19.6±0.4	20.8±0.2
%OC	6.4±0.5	11.5±0.3	12.2±0.2	13.4±0.2	14.1±0.2	11.2±0.2	12.1±0.3	12.2±0.3	12.2±0.4
%N	2.1±0.1	7.3±0.4	7.08±0.2	7.5±0.4	7.4±0.2	7.0±0.3	7.4±0.1	7.3±0.2	7.1±0.2
P(meq/100g)	1.5±0.1	1.1±1.3	1.2±0.6	3.7±0.2	3.7±0.2	1.2±0.1	1.4±0.2	2.3±1.0	2.6±1.3
Mg(meq/100g)	4.1±0.1	3.0±0.7	3.4±0.5	10±0.3	10.6±0.2	3.4±0.5	3.8±0.3	6.2±0.2	6.5±0.12
Ca(meq/100g)	6.9±0.4	8.0±1.4	8.6±0.3	12±0.7	12.6±0.1	8.6±0.3	10.2±0.3	10.8±0.5	13.5±1.2
K(meq/100g)	10.1±0.1	7.4±1.0	8.0±0.1	9.8±0.8	11.1±1.3	8.0±0.1	9.4±0.3	10.4±0.4	10.4±4.4
Na(meq/100g)	9.9±0.0	13.4±0.4	14.1±0.1	19.6±0.2	22.3±0.3	14.1±0.1	20.8±0.5	30.8±0.5	32.2±2.1
CEC (meq/100g)	30.835	31.8	34.06	51.4	56.6	34.06	44.2	58.14	62.4

Discussion

The results of the physicochemical properties of the soil amended with cassava mill effluent is presented in table 3 above. Result shows an improved pH from 6.2 to 6.4 with optimum value of 6.4 obtained with 30% amendment after 6 months' post-treatment analysis. The ideal pH value for a good agricultural soil according to Laboratory Testing Procedure for Soil and Water Sample Analysis (2009), is 6.2-7.5. The values obtained from the soil sample for the heavy metals shows that Fe content reduced from 145±0.2 to 113.2mg/kg at 10% after 6months. Cu content reduced from 11.2 to 8.5mg/kg at 40% after 3 months. Zn content increased from 8.2 to 20.6mg/kg at 40% after 6months. Mn content increased from 12.1 to 24.3mg/kg at 40% after 3 months and Pb content reduced from 14.7 to 1.0mg/kg at 10% after 3 months. with the Organic carbon content of the soil increased from 6.4 and peaked at 14.1% with 40%k treatment after 3 months. CEC of the soil increased from 30.8 to peaked at 62.4 (meq/100g) with 40% treatment after 6 months. This result is consistent with the findings of Ebhoaye and Dada (2004), Akpan, *et al*, (2011) and also, Nweke and Onuoha (2024), where cassava mill effluents increased soil physicochemical properties in almost all cases of their interactions. According World Health Organisation (WHO, 2004) the permissive levels for Fe, Cu, Zn, Mn and Pb in the soil is 5,000mg/kg, 36mg/kg, 300mg/kg, 400 mg/kg and 85 mg/kg respectively. So, the heavy metals content of the treated soil samples were also within permissive levels.

Conclusion

Results revealed an increase in soil fertility indicators like the pH, organic carbon and CEC. In conclusion, cassava mill effluent, which hitherto had been a soil contaminant can be deliberately added to the soil to improve its fertility over time. It also showed that the cassava mill effluent had significant impacts on the heavy metals content of the soil samples. While it increased the Zn and Mn content of the soil sample, it reduced the Fe, Pb and Cu content of the soil. However, the outcome of all reactions showed they were within specifications.

Recommendation

The addition of cassava mill effluent for the purpose of soil fertility improvement should be between 3-6months interval with 40% mixture with soil sample. However, precaution must be taken in its addition to soils with high metal content.

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